

FREEDOM AND SECURITY: AN ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIP IN THE LIGHT OF FREIREAN PEDAGOGY AND ETHNOMATHEMATICS

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Abstract

In this text, the author explores the complex relationship between freedom and security in education based on the theoretical framework of Paulo Freire's work on education as the practice of freedom and Ubiratan D'Ambrosio's ethnomathematics. According to Freire, education should be seen as a practice of freedom that frees people from their oppressions, allowing them to exercise their freedom of thought and action. D'Ambrosio's ethnomathematics is an approach to mathematics education that focuses on the connection between mathematics and culture, seeking to respect and value cultural diversity. Both Freire and D'Ambrosio emphasize the importance of cultural diversity and need to respect different ways of thinking and solving problems. However, the relationship between freedom and security in education is complex, as excessive focus on security can restrict the freedom and creativity of students. Therefore, it is necessary to find a balance between freedom and security in education. Teachers should promote critical development in their students, allowing them to mobilize knowledge to solve their everyday problems and enjoy their freedom without giving up their security. Overall, the text highlights the importance of considering the relationship between freedom and security in education, and the need to find a balance between them to promote critical thinking and respect for cultural diversity.

Key words: freedom, security, education, Paulo Freire, ethnomathematics, liberation, cultural diversity, critical thinking.

The relationship between freedom and security is a complex and important issue that involves many aspects of human life, including education. In this text, we propose to explore the relationship between freedom and security in education based on the

theoretical framework of Paulo Freire's work on education as the practice of freedom and Ubiratan D'Ambrosio's ethnomathematics. In the Brazilian educational context, Freire has a relevant role, specially to redefine the relationship between the teachers and their pupils. However, D'Ambrosio was an important mathematical educator that has developed the concept of ethnomathematics, which will be explained.

Paulo Freire, one of the main educational thinkers of the 20th century, focuses his work on the concept of liberation. In his work "Pedagogy of the Oppressed", Freire (2017) argues that education should be seen as a practice of freedom capable of freeing people from their oppressions. Education is a dialogical process in which students become active subjects of their own learning and social transformation. In this sense, education should be liberating, allowing people to exercise their freedom of thought and action.

Freire (2017) argues that people need to be literate not based on phonetic stereotypes, but through objects and practices that are part of their daily lives. These objects and practices, called generative themes by Freire (2017), gain meaning in the imaginary of literacy learners, as they belong to the set of life experiences of these individuals. Freire (2017) states that it is necessary to overcome the mere reading of letters and words and provide learners with tools to carry out a reading of the world, preferably a critical one.

Ethnomathematics, developed by Ubiratan D'Ambrosio, is an approach to mathematics education that focuses on the connection between mathematics and culture. According to D'Ambrosio (2017), mathematics is a form of knowledge that is socially constructed and varies according to different cultures. Ethnomathematics seeks to respect and value cultural diversity, taking into account different ways of thinking and solving mathematical problems.

Ethnomathematics is an important part of the subject's mathematics education, as it involves the set of knowledge mobilized in problem solving. D'Ambrosio (1996) states that "all knowledge is the result of a long cumulative generation process [...]". (p. 18). In this sense, when dealing with ethnomathematics, the author refers to the worldview developed over this cumulative process.

D'Ambrosio too reflects about the relationship between the ethnomathematics and the STEAM education movement (D'Ambrosio, 2020). In that work, the author argues that the interdisciplinary process of STEAM education can be linked to ethnomathematics, that is an interdisciplinary vision of mathematics.

Epistemologically, ethnomathematics can be embased in Feyerabend's epistemology. Dos Santos et al. (2018) has established this relationship, when it argues that the ethnomathematics was constructed as a valid discourse of the individuals, that integrates a cultural or ethnic group. Dos Santos et al. (2018) makes a parallel between the ethnomathematical interpretation of that discourse and the "all is valid" vision of Paul Feyerabend.

The relationship between Freire's education as the practice of freedom and D'Ambrosio's ethnomathematics can be seen from their common view that education should be liberating and respect cultural diversity. Freire's liberating education seeks to free people from their oppressions and allow them to exercise their freedom of thought and action. D'Ambrosio's ethnomathematics seeks to respect and value cultural diversity, taking into account different ways of thinking and solving mathematical problems.

However, the relationship between freedom and security in education is complex, as freedom can be seen as a value to be protected, but security is also important to ensure a safe and healthy environment for students. For Freire (2019), security can be seen as a prerequisite for freedom, as people can only exercise their freedom when they feel secure. Ethnomathematics also emphasizes the importance of cultural security, that is, the need to ensure that different cultures are respected and valued. However, an excessive focus on security can restrict the freedom and creativity of students, limiting their ability to think critically and autonomously. Therefore, it is necessary to find a balance between freedom and security in education.

In this sense, it is essential that teachers promote critical development in their students. With this, they can decide how to promote the balance between freedom and security, mobilizing knowledge to solve their everyday problems, allowing them to fully enjoy their freedom without giving up their security.

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